

SEMANTIC PARALLELISM AND NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the issues of semantic parallelism and national peculiarities in phraseological units. Phraseological units are among the most expressive elements of language, reflecting a nation's culture, way of thinking, and historical experience. The article examines the phenomenon of semantic parallelism among phraseological expressions in different languages, how they are shaped under the influence of genealogical, areal, and cultural factors, and how they express national mentality. Additionally, the linguistic and cultural features of phraseological expressions, their role in translation, and their significance in intercultural communication are discussed.*

Keywords: *Phraseological units, semantic parallelism, national peculiarities, linguistic and cultural studies, phraseological application, metaphorical units, national mentality, intercultural communication, translation studies.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada frazeologik birliklardagi semantik parallelizm va milliy o'ziga xoslik masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Frazeologik birliklar tilning eng ifodali unsurlaridan biri bo'lib, xalqning madaniyati, tafakkuri va tarixiy tajribasini aks ettiradi. Maqolada turli tillardagi frazeologik iboralar o'rtasidagi semantik parallelizm hodisasi, ularning genealogik, areal va madaniy omillar ta'sirida qanday shakllangani hamda milliy mentalitetni qanday ifodalashi yoritiladi. Shuningdek, frazeologizmlarning lingvistik va madaniy xususiyatlari, tarjima jarayonidagi o'rni va madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Frazeologik birliklar, semantik parallelizm, milliy o'ziga xoslik, lingvokulturologiya, frazeologik aplikatsiya, metaforik birliklar, xalq tafakkuri, madaniyatlararo muloqot, tarjimashunoslik.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются вопросы семантического параллелизма и национальной специфики фразеологических единиц. Фразеологические единицы являются одними из самых выразительных элементов языка, отражая культуру, мышление и исторический опыт народа. В статье рассматривается феномен семантического параллелизма среди фразеологических выражений в разных языках, их формирование под влиянием генеалогических, ареальных и культурных факторов, а также их роль в выражении национального менталитета. Кроме того, анализируются лингвистические и культурные особенности фразеологических выражений, их роль в процессе перевода и значение в межкультурной коммуникации.*

Ключевые слова: *фразеологические единицы, семантический параллелизм, национальная специфика, лингвокультурология, фразеологическая аппликация, метафорические единицы, национальный менталитет, межкультурная коммуникация, переводоведение.*

Introduction: Phraseological units form an essential part of the language system and serve as a means of reflecting a nation's worldview, historical experience, and culture. These units stand out due to their fixed meanings, which are independent of the literal meanings of their

individual components. Through phraseological expressions, the way of thinking, values, and mentality of a people are revealed. Semantic parallelism in phraseological units allows for identifying similarities and differences between idiomatic expressions in different languages. For example, the Uzbek phrase *suvg'a tushgan mushukdek* (lit. like a cat fallen into water) is semantically similar to the Russian *как мокрая курица* (like a wet hen) and the English *like a drowned rat*. Such similarities indicate shared perceptions of natural phenomena and life experiences across different nations.

The national peculiarities of phraseological expressions, on the other hand, manifest in their components, preserving a nation's historical and cultural memory. For instance, while the Uzbek phrase *otning kallasidek* (as big as a horse's head) denotes largeness, its English counterpart is *as big as an elephant*. These differences arise due to the unique environmental and cultural contexts of each nation. Phraseological units occupy a special place among the expressive means of language. They are not only rich in meaning and imagery but also reflect the culture, way of thinking, and historical experience of a people. Unlike the meanings of their individual components, phraseological units convey a general sense that is often the result of national wisdom and figurative thinking. These expressions enhance the emotional and aesthetic impact of language while also highlighting national identity. Furthermore, semantic parallelism is observed in phraseological expressions across different languages, offering insights into linguistic and cultural similarities and differences.

Semantic parallelism refers to the phenomenon in which phraseological units in different languages have similar or equivalent meanings. This phenomenon reflects shared cognitive structures and may have emerged as a result of intercultural interactions. In some cases, semantic parallelism is more common among genealogically or a really related languages, but it can also be found in structurally distinct languages. For example, the Uzbek phrase *suvg'a tushgan mushukdek* corresponds in meaning to the Russian *как мокрая курица*, both conveying a sense of dejection or helplessness. These parallels demonstrate the convergence of worldviews, attitudes toward natural phenomena, and life experiences across different nations. A new approach to phraseology is associated with the works of V.V. Vinogradov, particularly with his concept of bound lexical meaning. The inclusion of this concept in phraseology has yet to be fully evaluated in both domestic and foreign linguistic research. In this phenomenon, some components of phraseological units retain their free meanings independently of context, while others acquire bound meanings, which emerge only in combination with specific words.[1] For example, in Uzbek, expressions like *yurak yutmoq* (to summon courage), *ko'ngli tushmoq* (to feel down), and *boshi osmonga yetmoq* (to be extremely happy) exist, but constructions such as *yurak to'kmoq* or *boshi yerdan chiqmoq* do not sound natural. Similarly, in English, phrases like *to break the silence*, *to break the news*, and *to break a habit* are common, whereas *to break the happiness* or *to break the sadness* are not. The uniqueness of such phraseological units lies in the fact that their bound lexical meanings emerge only in connection with specific concepts and word forms. This limitation is not derived from the logical or objective nature of concepts but rather from the historical and cultural factors shaping the language system.

Sh. Bally interprets the interdependence of meanings within phraseological units in a metaphorical manner. According to him, abstract nouns, adjectives, and verbs retain their independence while appearing linked due to conventional usage. In such cases, the bound word often serves to enhance the primary meaning without altering its essence.[2] While some components of phraseological units maintain a degree of independence, their traditional association with other components creates semantic cohesion. In linguistics, stylistic typologies

of phraseological units have also been proposed. The classification of phraseological expressions based on their expressive-stylistic properties does not fundamentally differ from the classification of individual words from the same perspective. Therefore, when discussing phraseological expressions, it is essential to consider how their evaluative, emotional, and expressive characteristics develop depending on the speech domain and intended purpose.[3] Some phraseological units have specific stylistic constraints, being used only in particular speech styles or contexts.

B.A.Larin attempted to systematize phraseological units from a historical perspective, categorizing them into three main types: variable expressions, metaphorical expressions, and idioms. This classification is significant for understanding the formation mechanisms of phraseological units and identifying their semantic parallels.[4] V.N.Teliya devoted special attention to the linguistic and cultural peculiarities of phraseological units. According to her, the cultural and national characteristics of idioms are interpreted within a cultural context through their semantics. Each nation expresses its national mentality, values, and cultural heritage through phraseological units. Therefore, studying the semantic parallelism and national peculiarities of phraseological units is of great importance in linguistic and cultural studies.[5]

Conclusion: The semantic parallelism and national peculiarities of phraseological units hold great significance in linguistics, translation studies, and cultural research. While phraseological expressions in different languages may be equivalent in meaning, their components and semantic features are closely tied to national mentality and historical experience. Consequently, finding direct equivalents during translation can be challenging, requiring a deep understanding of cultural context. Studying semantic parallelism in phraseological units remains a crucial topic in intercultural communication, translation theory, and linguistic and cultural studies. Future research should focus on a deeper analysis of the semantic and stylistic aspects of phraseological expressions, exploring how they are formed in different languages and how cultural aspects can be effectively considered in translation.

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